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The first record of the ant *Temnothorax tesquorum* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) in Ukraine

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Radchenko, A. G. The first record of the ant *Temnothorax tesquorum* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) in Ukraine. Summary. — Data on distribution of *Temnothorax tesquorum* (Arnoldi, 1977) in general, and in Ukraine particularly, is provided. This species is characterized first of all by the unicolorous brownish body; the differences between it and the second brownish species from the Ukrainian fauna, *T. jailensis*, are given.

Key words: ants, Formicidae, distribution, fauna, taxonomy, Ukraine.

Радченко, О. Г. Перша знахідка мурашки *Temnothorax tesquorum* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) в Україні. Резюме. — Наведено дані про загальне поширення *Temnothorax tesquorum* (Arnoldi, 1977) та в Україні зокрема. Цей вид характеризується перш за все однобарвним брунатним тілом; показані відмінності між ним і другим брунатним видом української фауни, *T. jailensis*.

Ключові слова: мурашки, Formicidae, поширення, фауна, таксономія, Україна.

Introduction

The genus *Temnothorax* is among the most speciose ant genera, comprising more than 400 described species distributed worldwide except for Australia and Madagascar. At the same time, more than half of species are known from the Palaearctic, and about one third are from the Nearctic Region.

Temnothorax tesquorum was collected by K. V. Arnoldi in 1927 in Salsk steppes (Rostov Region, Russia), but described much later based on three workers (Arnoldi, 1977). It is characterized by the dark brown body, elongated head with subparallel sides, long scapes that are almost reaching occipital margin of the head, quite long propodeal teeth, widely rounded dorsum of the petiolar node, and densely sculptured head dorsum, mesosoma and waist.

This quite rare steppe species was known till recently from the type locality and northern Kazakhstan. It is necessary to notice that Bolton (2019) erroneously recorded the type locality of *T. tesquorum* as Georgia, and this species by unknown reason is missed in the modern catalogue of Russian ants (Dubovikoff & Yusupov, 2017). After careful reinvestigation of various materials from Ukraine I found two workers of *T. tesquorum* collected in the Askania-Nova Biosphere Reserve, Kherson Region of Ukraine.

Material and methods

I investigated the holotype and two paratype specimens of *T. tesquorum* and three workers from the northern Kazakhstan; all of them are preserved in the collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow State University (ZMMU). For comparison I examined the paratype specimen of *T. jailensis* Arnoldi, 1977 (preserved in ZMMU) as well as ten workers and one gyne of this species from Crimea (preserved in Schmalhausen Institute of zoology NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv).

For more detailed comparison of *T. tesquorum* and *T. jailensis* some measurements to calculate ratios are used: HL — maximum length of the head in dorsal view, measured in a straight line from the anteriormost point of clypeus to the mid-point of occipital margin; HW — maximum width of the head in dorsal view behind (above) the eyes; SL — maximum length of the scape measured in a straight line from its apex to the articulation with condylar bulb.

Results

Material. Ukraine, Kherson Region, Chaplynka District, Askania-Nova Biosphere Reserve, steppe, July 1983, 2 workers (A. Radchenko).

Distribution in Ukraine. Kherson Reg., Askania-Nova Biosphere Reserve.

Comparative analysis

Seventeen *Temnothorax* species are known in Ukraine nowadays (Radchenko, 2016), and only two of them have unicolorous brownish body: *T. tesquorum* and Crimean endemic *T. jaiensis*. They well differ from each other not only by the set of morphological features, but also by the ecological preferences: the first species inhabit steppes, and the latter one is forest dweller, making nests in dry tree branches or wood remnants.

The main morphological difference between *T. tesquorum* and *T. jaiensis* (workers) are:

<i>T. tesquorum</i>	<i>T. jaiensis</i>
Whole head dorsum quite coarsely sculptured, with longitudinal rugae and punctuation (Fig. 2)	Only frons partly with not coarse longitudinal rugulosity, posterior half of head dorsum superficially punctured or smooth (Fig. 4)
Head more elongate (HL/HW > 1.20), with subparallel sides (Fig. 2)	Head shorter (HL/HW < 1.17), with somewhat convex sides (Fig. 4)
Antennal scape longer, almost reaching occipital margin, SL/HL > 1.80 (Fig. 2)	Antennal scape shorter, far not reaching occipital margin, SL/HL < 1.75 (Fig. 4)
Propodeum with long teeth; petiole with widely rounded node dorsum (Fig. 1)	Propodeum with short sharp denticles; petiole with flattened node dorsum (Fig. 3)

Figs 1–4. Images of *Temnothorax tesquorum* (1, 2) and *T. jaiensis* (3, 4); 1, 3 — body, lateral view; 2, 4 — head, dorsal view.

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